

A MODERN APPROACH TO THE PREVENTION OF CERVICAL PATHOLOGY

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Abstract. *The problem of cervical disease has a significant impact on women's reproductive health. But the main problem is different: background diseases present in the cervix at a certain point can lead to the development of a malignant process. Meanwhile, cervical cancer ranks third in frequency among diseases of the reproductive system. Most cases of cervical cancer (78%) occur in developing countries. A comprehensive laboratory study and analysis of the obstetric and gynecological status of patients with cervical pathology aged 18 to 43 years for 2023 was conducted at the antenatal clinic of Polyclinic No. 1 in Fergana. The causes of cervical pathology were analyzed in detail. Hormonal status was examined using radioimmunoassay - progesterone, human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), thyroid hormones - triiodothyronine, thyroxine, thyroid-stimulating hormone - were examined using enzyme immunoassay. To identify pathology, the Schiller test, colposcopy, cytology and histology tests were performed. A smear for flora and tests for latent infections were also mandatory.*

Keywords: *cervical cancer, human papillomavirus (HPV).*

Actuality. Cervical diseases are among the most common conditions within the structure of reproductive health. This is because they significantly impact women's reproductive activity. However, the main issue lies elsewhere: all underlying diseases may, at some point, lead to malignancy. Cervical cancer ranks third in prevalence among reproductive system diseases. [1] There are various types of cervical pathologies, which can be divided into three main groups: benign conditions, precancerous, and cancerous. The first group includes cervical erosion, ectopy, polyps, and leukoplakia. Precancerous conditions are primarily represented by different types of cervical dysplasia. It is important to note that each type of cervical pathology has its own causes and pathogenesis. [2]

Cervical ectopy is characterized by the displacement of columnar epithelium onto the vaginal portion of the cervix. There are two types: congenital ectopy and acquired ectopy. In the first case, the name speaks for itself, while in the latter, the causes may include mechanical damage, inflammation, or hormonal imbalance. Symptoms may include bloody discharge during or after intercourse or increased vaginal discharge.

Leukoplakia of the cervix is not well understood in terms of its causes. However, two forms are distinguished: thin leukoplakia and thick leukoplakia, with the latter being less common.

Condylomas, which may progress to cancer, are caused by human papillomavirus (HPV), which is sexually transmitted. [3]

Cervical dysplasia involves pathological changes in the tissue and can arise in response to sexually transmitted and infectious diseases. Dysplasia is classified into three grades of severity. Risk factors include:

Early initiation of sexual activity

Childbirth before the age of 16

Multiple sexual partners (especially without protection)

A high number of abortions
Reduced immunity and vitamin deficiencies
Smoking

Cervical carcinoma or cancer often remains asymptomatic for a long time, which explains its high prevalence. [4] Regular gynecological check-ups are therefore crucial to monitor cervical health.

Objective. To determine the prevalence of cervical pathologies among pregnant women and to evaluate diagnostic and treatment methods for these conditions.

Materials and Methods. A comprehensive laboratory study and analysis of the obstetric and gynecological status of patients with cervical pathology aged 18 to 43 years was conducted in 2023 at the Women's Health Clinic No. 1 in Fergana. The causes of cervical pathology were analyzed in detail. Hormonal status (progesterone and human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG)) was examined using radioimmunoassay and thyroid hormones (triiodothyronine, thyroxine, and thyroid-stimulating hormone) - through enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. To identify pathologies, Schiller's test, colposcopy, and cytological and histological analyses were performed. Vaginal swabs for flora and tests for hidden infections were mandatory. HPV diagnosis included testing for sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Ultrasound scanning (US) with cervical length measurement was also conducted.

A total of 2,046 patients were registered at the Women's Health Clinic. Of these, colposcopy was performed on 1,317 patients (64%). Cervical pathology was identified only in 265 patients, representing 20% of all those who visited the clinic over the course of one calendar year. All patients were divided into five groups based on the type of pathology as per the classification above.

Results. The first group consisted of 236 patients (84%) with ectopy, of whom 9 (4%) were pregnant at different stages. These women underwent regular Schiller's tests, during which the vaginal portion of the cervix was stained with iodine-based preparations. During extended colposcopy with 5% iodine solution, affected areas turned light pink. Targeted biopsies were mandatory. [5]

The second group included 21 patients (7%) with leukoplakia, only one of whom was pregnant. Among them, thin leukoplakia was detected in 18 patients, and thick leukoplakia in 3. Histological examination is considered the gold standard for diagnosis, mainly using Pap smears or biopsy. Treatment involved laser coagulation of affected areas, and in severe cases, cervical conization was performed.

The third group comprised 7 patients (2%) with condylomas. HPV was detected in all patients using PCR diagnostics. No pregnant women were included in this group. Treatment involved laser therapy, radio wave techniques, and electrocoagulation. After HPV detection, antiviral therapy was prescribed in the form of "Panavir" suppositories, administered in three 10-day cycles followed by colposcopy. In most cases, the virus was not detected upon reexamination.

The fourth group included 15 patients (5%) with cervical dysplasia, of whom 10 had Grade 1 dysplasia, 3 had Grade 2, and 2 had Grade 3. Antiviral therapy combined with anti-inflammatory therapy in the form of suppositories was prescribed. Surgical treatment was performed in the absence of contraindications.

The last group included 3 patients (1%) diagnosed with cervical carcinoma, one of whom was pregnant. Treatment was carried out at the Regional Oncology Center in Fergana and involved

cervical excision. For young women planning to conceive, cervical conization or radio wave destruction was performed when possible.

In total, 46 diathermocoagulations, 20 ozone therapies, and 30 laser coagulations were performed in the Women's Health Clinic over the year. After appropriate treatment, the number of recurrences was very low. In all cases, cervical pathology treatment was carried out alongside treatment for associated conditions. For inflammatory etiologies, the causative agent was identified, and treatment was conducted accordingly.

Special attention was given to the treatment of cervical diseases in nulliparous and pregnant women. Many treatment methods for these pathologies can leave scars on the cervix, which can significantly complicate childbirth.

Conclusions. Our analysis of cervical pathology prevalence revealed that many cases are detected at more advanced stages. This indicates that most women do not visit gynecologists regularly. Regular examinations can identify pathologies at an earlier stage. Cervical pathologies can lead to pregnancy loss, so reducing perinatal risks in these cases can be achieved through preconception planning, a thorough medical history assessment considering all risk factors, and pregravid preparation, including prescribing vitamin-mineral complexes with folic acid and micronized progesterone when necessary. In addition to pregravid counseling, initial examinations should be conducted at least three months before the intended conception, along with preventive measures and, if necessary, in-depth diagnostics and treatment.

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